

dE=TdS as the Maximum Entropy Principle For a Power Law Probability

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In (1) a power law probability $p(e) = (e/T)^{-g} / Z$ is assumed and the first law of thermodynamics $dE=TdS$ utilized to obtain a form for the entropy density as a function of $p(e)$. The main idea of (1) seems to be that dE and dS only change due to changes in $p(e)$ and not due to a parameter (which may alter coefficients as well $p(e)$). The authors alter $p(e) \rightarrow p(e)+dp(e)$ such that $\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0$ ((1)). This form of change is applied to $dE-TdS$ to yield $\sum_i (e_i - T d/dp(G)) dp(e_i)$ ((2)) where G is entropy density. In (1) it is argued that $e_i - TdG/dp(e_i) = K = \text{constant}$ in order that ((2)) be the same as ((1)) up to a multiplicative constant. This equation may be integrated to ultimately find a solution for $G(p(e_i))$ and ultimately entropy. Temperature in this scenario is a constant which (1) writes in terms of e_o, e_m (the bounds of e) and g . In thermodynamics, T is a parameter which changes and measures the thermal properties of a system.

We argue that the approach using $dE=TdS$, employed in (1), is essentially the maximum entropy principle subject to the main constraint $\sum_i e_i p(e_i)$, because only $p(e_i)$ is varied. In such a case: $TdS-dE=0$ yields the main term of the entropy of (1). (A second term which is a constant time $p(e)$ is added, but $\int p(e)de=1$ so this term is a constant and $dE=TdS$ only defines entropy up to a constant. In (1) certain boundary conditions are used to determine this constant. Thus the main idea is to “maximize S subject to $1/T E$ by changing $p(e_i)$. This maximization process, however, is essentially equivalent to writing e_i/T in terms of $p(e_i)$ i.e. $\text{Function}(p(e_i))$. This function may be integrated with respect to $dp(e_i)$ so that the derivative then yields e_i/T , which when multiplied by T , yields e_i which, in turn, equals e_i from the constraint. Thus S is a mathematical function whose derivative with respect to $p(e_i)$ yields essentially e_i/T .

For a constant T temperature system, it is not clear that $dE=TdS$ is really a thermodynamic equation. In general T may change, but this means that dS involves changes in $p(e_i)$ due to a parameter in addition to changes in any coefficients which may be functions of this parameter. We show in the power law case that the coefficient in the function of $p(e_i)$, whose derivative with respect to $p(e_i)$ yields e_i/T , is in fact dependent on parameters which are linked to T . Thus $dE=TdS$ seems to be a maximization with respect to an energy constraint approach and not a thermodynamical one because the first law of thermodynamics does not stipulate that dE and dS change only through $p(e_i)$ only. In fact, in thermodynamics one does not need to write E and S in terms of $p(e_i)$. $p(e_i)$ enters when one thinks in terms of microscopic quantities.

Approach of (1) using $dE = TdS$, but Only Varying $p(e_i)$

The objective of (1) is to find the entropy for a power law probability given as:

$$p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^{-g} / Z(T) \quad ((3))$$

The traditional idea of using the variable $be_i = e_i/T$ is used even. The approach of (1) seems to be the following. The $p(e_i)$ are changed slightly (due to thermal changes and no work is done so e_i levels remain unchanged). Then:

$$\sum_i dp(e_i) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

This is a standard result which keeps the new probabilities normalized to 1. Next, the first law of thermodynamics (without work) is employed with dE and dS occurring because of changes in $p(e_i)$ only. Thus:

$$dE = TdS \longrightarrow \sum_i \{ e_i - T dG(p(e_i))/ dp(e_i) \} dp(e_i) \quad ((5))$$

Here $G(p(e_i))$ is the entropy density. The idea seems to be that ((4)) and ((5)) represent the same information, thus:

$$\{ e_i - T dG(p(e_i))/ dp(e_i) \} = K = \text{constant} \quad ((6)) \text{ so that } ((5)) \text{ is a multiple of } ((4))$$

((6)) is now a differential equation which may be integrated, albeit with the unknown constant K . Some explicit boundary conditions are added in (1) and an expression for entropy density is given as:

$$G(p(e_i)) = e_0/T \frac{1}{(1-1/g)} B^{-1/g} \{ \int dp \{-p + p^{1-1/g}\} \quad ((7))$$

E_0 represents a lower bound on e_i the single particle energy and:

$$B = Z (1/T)^{-g} \quad ((8))$$

When integrating ((4)), a constant term as well as the term proportional to $p e_i$ [in {} in ((7))] appear. Boundary conditions are used to set the constant to zero and fix the coefficient of p . It may be noted that $\int p dp = 1$, so the presence of p in g , the entropy density, is equivalent to a constant in S , the entropy. We do not focus on the constant or coefficient of p here, details may be found in (1) regarding the boundary condition used.

Point Regarding the Method of (1)

In (1), the idea of temperature T exists, but it is shown to depend on the parameters g , e_0 and e_m , the latter being the lower and upper bounds of e_i . (See equation 25 in (1).) Thus, if e_0, e_m and g are constant, T cannot change which is unusual for thermodynamics. Given that dS only changes through $p(e_i)$, while its coefficient, which contains e_0, e_m and g , does not change seems to indicate that the parameters are not changing. If one integrates entropy density, however, one is left with an entropy which is a function of these parameters. It seems that dS from thermodynamics can only change S based on these parameters, not on varying $p(e_i)$.

In general, a thermal change in the system means a change in T and hence $dp(e_i)/dT$. The point we wish to make is that entropy density $p(e_i)$ is not only a function of $p(e_i)$ which could in principle depend on T , but also of a coefficient which in itself may depend on T . Thus: $dE = \sum_i e_i dp(e_i)$, but $dS \rightarrow dG(p(e_i))/dp(e_i) dp(e_i)/dT + dG/dT$ (without touching $p(e_i)$). This latter term is not included in ((4)) suggesting that all constants are T independent which we later show is not the case. Thus, thermodynamics implies that a change dE or dS should be more general than simply changing $p(e_i)$. If one has a system with a constant T which cannot change, then it is not clear that this is a thermodynamical system. T temperature is supposed to be a parameter linked to thermal energy which is not measured by work. Thus we suggest that by only changing $p(e_i)$ it seems that one is applying some kind of maximization approach subject to constraints.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to an Energy Constraint

We argue that using the thermodynamical first law $dE=TdS$ and only varying $p(e_i)$ is identical to maximizing a function of $p(e_i)$, called entropy density, subject to the constraint $E= \sum_i e_i p(e_i)$. This in turn means that:

$$d/dp(e_i) \text{ entropy density} = e_i/T \quad ((10))$$

As a result, one may find e_i/T from an expression for $p(e_i)$ and then integrate this over $dp(e_i)$ so that the derivative $d/dp(e_i)$ undoes the integral and returns e_i/T which when multiplied by T equals e_i in the energy constraint.

Consider the case of the power law used in (1):

$p(e_i) = (e_i/T)^g / Z(T)$ ((11)) where $Z(T)$ is a normalization function of T and g is considered to be a given constant.

$$\text{Then:} \quad e_i/T = (pZ)^{-1/g} \quad ((12))$$

This form may be used to construct S density i.e.

$$S \text{ density} = p(e_i) (pZ)^{-1/g} + p(e_i) \text{ Function}(T) + \text{constant} \quad ((13))$$

S may include a constant term and a constant time $p(e_i)$ because $\int p(e_i) dp = 1$ which behaves as a constant in S . Thus the real key is the term in S shown in ((10)) whose derivative yields dE with variation with $p(e_i)$. The coefficient of this term is automatically given then.

To find such a term, the goal is to find an expression in $p(e_i)$ such that its derivative yields e_i/T . e_i/T is understood to be $e_i/T dp(e_i)$ if a derivative is taken. To find this, one first solves for e_i/T from a definition of the probability distribution and then integrates respect to $dp(e_i)$. This expression is given in ((12)) so integrating with respect to $dp(e_i)$ yields:

$$S \text{ term} = (p)^{-1/g+1} Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g) \quad ((14))$$

One may see that this matches the result of ((7)) from (1) with $e_0=1$ and B related to Z . Specifically, for $e_0=1$, $p(e_i) = e_i^{-g}/B = (be_i)^{-g}/Z$. Thus $Z^{-1/g} = bB^{-1/g}$ where $b=1/T$. If one considers the derivative of $(p)^{-1/g+1}$ with respect to p then:

$$d/dp (p)^{-1/g+1} = (-1/g + 1) b e_i (Z^{-1/g}) \quad ((15))$$

$$\text{The coefficient in front of this term is: } Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g) \quad ((16))$$

Thus $T d/db$ S term from ((13)) = e_i which is the required value. Thus:

$$S \text{ term} = (p)^{-1/g+1} Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g) \quad ((17))$$

This matches ((7)) from (1) and may be obtained almost immediately. The coefficient of the p term is taken to be the same due to boundary conditions.

Thermodynamics and a Parameter

In thermodynamics, T temperature is a parameter which may change. This change measures in part changes due to "heat" as opposed to mechanical work. Thermodynamics, it seems, is linked to the notion of heat as well as mechanical work from Newton's laws. Thus to have a constant T is unusual. In (1), T is given as a function of e_0, e_m and g . One may imagine systems with different g values and argue these have different average energies and so different temperatures. One might then consider changing E i.e. dE in terms of the parameter g . $E = \text{Sum over } i e_i p(e_i)$ so $dE/dg = \text{Sum over } i e_i dp/dg$. With entropy, however, matters become more complicated because entropy contains coefficients with g as well as $p(e_i)$ containing g . Thus it does not suffice to simply change entropy with respect to $p(e_i)$.

This, we argue, shows that $dE = TdS$ from thermodynamics parts ways with the maximization of entropy subject to an energy constraint. The latter only depends on changing $p(e_i)$. Thus, for the entropy given in (1), dE is not equal to TdS if one considers $dE = dE/dp dp/dg$ because $T dS/dp dp/dg dg$ cancels dE , but the coefficient of the powers of $p(e_i)$ in S , namely $Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g)$ is a function of g . Thus, instead:

$$dE = \text{Sum over } i e_i dp(e_i)/dg dg = T \text{ Sum over } i dS/dp dp/dg dg + T \text{ Sum over } i (p)^{-1/g+1} d/dg (Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g)) - T \text{ Sum over } i (p)^{-1/g+1} d/dg (Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g)) dg \quad ((18))$$

$$\text{In other words, } dE = TdS - T \text{ Sum over } i (p)^{-1/g+1} d/dg (Z^{-1/g} / (1-1/g)) dg \quad ((19))$$

which is the full form of the first law of thermodynamics.

Thus, the first law of thermodynamics without a work term does not hold for a variation in g .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that using the first law of thermodynamics without any work terms i.e. $dE=TdS$ and varying it with respect to $p(e_i)$ where $E= \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i p(e_i)$ is equivalent to the maximization of entropy subject to a constraint on energy. This maximization approach is equivalent to using $p(e_i/T)$ to find an expression for e_i/T i.e. $e_i/T = \text{Function}(p(e_i))$. This function may be integrated with respect to $dp(e_i)$ so that its derivative $d/dp(e_i)$ (under the maximization procedure) returns e_i/T with $1/T$ being equivalent to the Lagrange multiplier of E . Thus, entropy from the maximization approach follows a specific recipe. In (1), the terms with $p(e_i)$ to powers of g represent this maximization result. A second constant term is added. It is proportional to $p(e_i)$, but $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } p(e_i)=1$ so one really adds a constant which allows for S to satisfy some boundary conditions listed in (1).

The maximization approach which only varies $p(e_i)$, it seems, is independent from thermodynamics because thermodynamics calculates dE and dS as caused by the change in a parameter. For E , this is not an issue because $dE/dp(e_i) = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i dp/dg dg$, but for S there is an issue because $S = \text{Coefficient}(g) \text{ Sum over } i \text{ } (p)^{-1/g + 1}$. TdS then cancels dE when one takes $dS/dp dp/dg$, but there is a second term associated with $d/dg \text{ Coefficient}(g)$. Thus, $dE=TdS$ does not hold, it seems, for the case of varying a parameter like g . Rather, one needs the full first law of thermodynamics: $dE = TdS - Td\text{Coefficient}/dg dg$. As a result, the form $dE=TdS$ is really a maximization of entropy subject to an entropy constraint approach, we argue.

References

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